

IPCC FAIR data approach (Contribution to the Open Science and Data Help Desk at EGU 2024)

[00:00]

Introduction:

My name is Martina Stockhause, I will introduce our shared effort and experience with the implementation of the FAIR data principles into the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), from concept to challenges and recommendations and plans for the next cycle AR7. It complements the information from last year on the work of IPCC Working Group I Technical Support Unit (WGI TSU) and the IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC) Partners in implementing a new paradigm for data publication in the AR6 WGI report. This work has been elaborated in collaboration with the AR6 WGI TSU data team, the CEDA team, and our staff at DKRZ.

The IPCC, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, is the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change. It brings together scientists from all over the world to review the latest research and then make an expert assessment of the robustness of this knowledge. The IPCC does not conduct its own research but its reports are based on published scientific evidence, peer-reviewed literature and datasets. The three IPCC assessment reports provide important information that supports governments and decision-makers around the world in developing climate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

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WGI and FAIR principles:

The WGI of the IPCC recognizes the importance of open and transparent sharing of scientific data in the field of climate change research and as part of a robust and transparent IPCC assessment. By implementing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, WGI has ensured that much of their data and other digital resources are accessible to other scientists, researchers, practitioners, and policymakers around the world. The DDC Partners have devoted resources to ensure that the data is well-organized, well-documented, and preserved for long-term use according to best practices for repositories. These best practices are described in the criteria of the Core Trust Seal, which is an integral part of the application process for a Regular Membership of the World Data System (WDS).

Let me show you our FAIR approach in action with two examples:

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Walk-through online resources:

1. input data example;

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2. final data example

There is much more to discover about our IPCC FAIR data approach for example the IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas. You are invited to try it out yourself and to learn more details about our approach with the references provided.

[12:20] Challenges and AR7 Recommendations:

The collaborative FAIR data efforts of WGI TSU and DDC have resulted in numerous curated digital resources that are openly accessible and augment the AR6 WGI results with data and code. These resources can be accessed through the repositories of the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) and the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ), and through Zenodo, the IPCC WGI website, and the joint DDC catalog. In the last year, the user navigation between the resources has been enhanced by adding cross-references which closed dead ends.

We faced several challenges related to new organizational requirements and a lack of pre-existing tools across the workflow. These have been addressed in the AR7 recommendations and ongoing initial work:

1. Figure creation provenance information should be obtained from IPCC authors during the assessment process and should include all information required by the IPCC Data Guidelines. The Figure Manager could serve as a platform for providing this information, which is used for data referencing and data traceability.
2. A reference to information about figure creation should be part of the figure caption and figure pages to increase their transparency. The development is carried out together with the RDA Complex Citation WG.

Final words:

The implementation of FAIR data in the AR6 WGI has enhanced the transparency and accessibility of AR6 outcomes and first steps towards a workflow consolidation aiming at a more exhaustive and reliable data and software usage documentation in the upcoming AR7. I hope that this video has provided insight into our approach in the unique context of the IPCC.

[14:51]

References:

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IPCC Links:

IPCC: <https://www.ipcc.ch/>

IPCC WGI AR6: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>

IPCC WGI data and code access: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/data-access/>

IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas: <https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>

IPCC DDC: <https://www.ipcc-data.org>

Summary for All:

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/downloads/outreach/IPCC_AR6_WGI_SummaryForAll.pdf

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